

STUDIES IN THE SESQUITERPENE SERIES. PART I.
SYNTHESIS OF THE TRIETHYL ESTER OF
 $C_{15}H_{24}(CO_2H)_3$, OBTAINED FROM SELINENES.*

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A synthetic route has been developed for the synthesis of the tricarboxylic acid which has been obtained by the oxidation of selinenes. This method again offers the possibilities for the extension of the same for the synthesis of the naturally occurring selinenes and related bodies. One of the salient points of the scheme is the introduction of the carboxyl group at the required position in the *cyclohexane* ring through the condensation of oxalic ester according to the "Principle of Vinylogy."

As much of the evidence for the existence of the angular methyl group in the sesquiterpenes is indirect, being based on the isoprene rule, it appeared that the synthetical experiments in the eudesmol group are necessary to supplement the analytical evidences of Ruzicka and his co-workers. The first successful synthetic attempt in this group is due to Simonsen (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 1138), who prepared a hydrogenated sesquiterpene ketone belonging to the eudesmol group.

Ruzicka, Koolhaus and Wing (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1931, **14**, 1151, 1171) have shown that the sesquiterpenes of the selinene group belong to the *cis*-decalin series. It is known that the *trans*-fusion of one *cyclohexane* ring to another in the *ortho*-position is stable. The *cis*-fusion results in an unstable arrangement which easily isomerises to the *trans*-form at high temperatures. Moreover, physical measurements, *e.g.* heat of combustion, etc., also prove the *cis*-form to be the less stable form (Roth and Lasse, *Annalen*, 1925, **451**, 48). The stability of the *cis*-linking arises through the presence of an angular methyl group. Similarly, in the *bicyclo*-octane series, methyl group stabilises the unstable 8-methyl-*bicyclo*-octane derivatives (Wieland and Dane, *J. physiol. Chem.*, 1933, **216**, 91). These observations have led Huckel to the view that the strain theory cannot be applied in a simple manner to the *bicyclo* systems (Mills, "Reports of the Fourth Solvay Conference," 1931, p. 16). Hence to realise an actual synthesis of these bodies the possibilities of the formation of various isomers at intermediate stages should be avoided so that the disturbing factor of stereoisomerism is minimised to an appreciable extent.

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A possible method has now been developed for the synthesis of selinic acid (Semmler *et al.*, *Ber.*, 1912, **45**, 3031, 3725; 1913, **46**, 599) which has been tentatively formulated by Ruzicka (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1922, **5**, 345) as (I).

It is evident that it can exist in four stereochemical forms and its actual synthesis will also finally establish the presence of the angular methyl group with all its stereochemical implications.

Chloromethyl ether does not condense with *o*-methylcyclohexanone in presence of sodamide in ethereal solution (*cf.* Haller and Cornubert, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1927, **41**, 367) and hence the lactone (II, $n=1$) could not be prepared, where the two rings in the lactone (II, $n=1$) should have *cis*-locking (*cf.* Hückel, *Annalen*, 1934, **514**, 240; Linstead, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 481). By this procedure, two possibilities out of four are ruled out and we are left only with the following possibilities :

- (i) COOH and the lactone group in *cis*-configuration,
- (ii) COOH and the lactone group in *trans*-configuration.

Further, as the hydroxy-dicarboxylic acid corresponding to the lactone acid (II, $n=1$; R=H) is a substituted *isophthalic* acid, the two carboxyl groups in it are interconvertible under standard conditions. It may be mentioned in this connection that there is no reference in the existing literature as regards the actual stereoisomerism of the *isopropylene* group with respect to the angular methyl group or the other ring of the decalin system in the selinenes and related bodies.

Attempts to condense ethoxyethyl chloride with *o*-methylcyclohexanone failed to give (II, $n=2$) but ethoxyethyl iodide smoothly reacts with the ketone under the usual conditions. As the product of condensation consists mainly of 1 : 1-disubstituted cyclohexan-2-one and a little of the 1 : 3-isomer, it is purified according to Ruzicka's method (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1931, **14**, 1169) by condensing with oxalic ester and then Simonsen's modification (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 1140) being followed for the isolation of the oxalo-derivative. The oxalo-derivative, thus obtained, is hydrolysed with baryta and the ketone (III) regenerated and converted into the related cyanohydrin in a quantitative yield with liquid hydrocyanic acid. The cyanohydrin is unusually stable, confirming Lapworth and Manske's views on the effect of α -alkylation (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 1976). The cyanohydrin is dehydrated with thionyl chloride and pyridine. The unsaturated nitrile (IV) is freed from sulphur by heating with precipitated copper in benzene. This method is decidedly an advantage over Simonsen's procedure of removing sulphur compounds by allowing to stand over aluminium-mercury couple for

several days. The purified unsaturated nitrile condenses smoothly with ethyl oxalate in presence of potassium ethoxide (Lapworth, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1901, 79, 1265; Kuhn *et al.*, *Ber.*, 1937, 70, 70, *et seq.*) and the yield of the condensation product is improved by using anhydrous pyridine as diluent (*cf. Ber.*, 1937, 70, 1148). The condensation product (V), isolated by vacuum distillation, is hydrolysed in methyl alcoholic solution with potassium hydroxide solution.

The pyruvic acid has been oxidised with hydrogen peroxide in pyridine solution in satisfactory yield, the other usual methods proving unsuccessful. The unsaturated cyano-acid, thus obtained, is reduced with sodium amalgam and isolated as the methyl ester (VI) after esterification. Hydrolysis of the cyano group and simultaneous de-ethoxylation have been carried out with hydrobromic acid. The product may be the lactonic acid (II, $n=1$; $R=H$) together with the corresponding bromodibasic acid. Consequently the mixture is directly treated with phosphorus pentabromide in the cold and subsequently treated with alcohol. From the reaction mixture the ester (VII, $R=Br$) is isolated in moderate yield together with a lower boiling fraction, which is most probably the lactonic ester (II, $n=1$; $R=Et$); the structure could not be definitely established, yield being too small. Replacement of the bromine atom by a cyano group has been carried out by the method of Rydon (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1341). The cyano compound is directly esterified and the triester (VIII, $R=CO_2Et$) has been isolated in very poor yield. Further work is in progress.

The bromo-ester (VII, $R=Br$) can be condensed with ethyl malonate for the synthesis of 9-methyldecalin systems which would lead to hydrogenated selinenes.

(V)

(VI)

(VII)

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

β-Ethoxyethyl Chloride.—To a mixture of glycol monoethyl ether (180 g.) and pyridine (160 g.), cooled in ice, was added slowly with constant shaking thionyl chloride (250 g.). After standing overnight, the mixture was heated on the water-bath for 1 hour. After cooling, the chloride was decanted off from pyridine hydrochloride and the latter, after decomposition with ice, was extracted with ether. The combined ethereal extracts and the chloride were washed with acid and alkali, and fractionated, b.p. 108–110°. It was converted into iodide, b.p. 151–54°, by refluxing with sodium iodide in alcoholic solution in the usual way.

1-Methyl-1-β-ethoxyethylcyclohexan-2-one (III).—A mixture of 2-methylcyclohexanone (112 g.) and finely powdered sodamide (45 g.) in ether (1200 c.c.) was heated under reflux with stirring for 5 hours. After 2 hours the volume of ether was gradually reduced to about 500 c.c., the mixture cooled in ice and ethoxyethyl iodide (200 g.) added in the course of 50 minutes. The temperature was gradually raised and the solution refluxed for another 5 hours, in such a manner that most of the ether evaporated off, for condensation with ethoxyethyl iodide proceeded better in concentrated solution. After standing overnight, the residue was decomposed with ice,

the ethereal layer separated and the aqueous portion extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was dried and low boiling fractions were removed at atmospheric pressure. From the residue, the fraction boiling at $95-110^{\circ}/8$ mm. was collected. On redistillation it had b.p. $100-105^{\circ}/5$ mm. (mainly $103^{\circ}/6$ mm.), yield 75 g. (Found : C, 71.4; H, 10.7. $C_{11}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 71.6; H, 10.8 per cent).

To a solution of sodium (7.6 g.) in alcohol (100 c.c.) cooled in a freezing mixture a cooled mixture of the above ketone (53 g.) and ethyl oxalate (42.4 c.c.) was added with thorough shaking, when a thick reddish brown solution was obtained. After standing overnight, the product was poured into ice and the alkaline solution was extracted with ether. The crude reddish oil from ether was hydrolysed on the water-bath with barium hydroxide (128 g.) and water (600 c.c.) for 4 hours. The precipitated solids were collected and washed with ether. The aqueous portion was also extracted with ether. The combined ethereal extract was dried and the solvent removed when the ketone was obtained. The precipitated barium salts were decomposed with ice and hydrochloric acid, barium chloride filtered off and the aqueous portion was thoroughly extracted with ether. The reddish oil, left after removal of the solvent, was again hydrolysed with baryta solution. The over-all yield of the ketone is 35 g., b.p. $100^{\circ}/6$ mm. (Found : C, 71.8; H, 10.42. $C_{11}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 71.6; H, 10.8 per cent).

The neutral fraction from the oxalic ester condensation was worked up in the usual way and only a small quantity of ketone was obtained which showed that the condensation had resulted mainly in the production of the 1 : 1-isomer.

The *semicarbazone*, prepared in the usual way, crystallised from dilute alcohol in sandy crystals, m.p. 122° . (Found : N, 17.5. $C_{11}H_{21}O_2N_2$ requires N, 17.0 per cent).

1-Methyl-1- β -ethoxyethylcyclohexanone-2-cyanohydrin.— The above ketone (12 g.), to which a drop of potassium cyanide solution had been added as a condensing agent, was cooled to -10° and hydrogen cyanide, generated from potassium cyanide (45 g.) and dilute sulphuric acid (45 c.c. H_2SO_4 ; 60 c.c. H_2O), was slowly passed into the ketone in the course of 1 hour. After standing overnight at 0° the solution was acidified with ice-cold sulphuric acid and a current of air passed through it to remove unreacted hydrogen cyanide. Finally it was extracted with ether, the extract dried over sodium sulphate and after the addition of a drop of sulphuric acid

distilled, 147°/9 mm., yield 13 g. (Found : N, 7·2. $C_{12}H_{21}O_2N$ requires N, 6·7 per cent):

1-Methyl-1-β-ethoxyethyl-2-cyano-Δ²-cyclohexene (IV).—A mixture of pyridine (5·9 c.c.) and the cyanohydrin (5 g.) was cooled in a freezing mixture and thionyl chloride (6 c.c.) was gradually added with thorough shaking and the solution was allowed to stand overnight when two layers were formed. The mixture was heated on the water-bath for 2 hours, cooled and the upper layer extracted with sodium-dried ether to avoid the formation of persistent emulsion. The plastic mass left was decomposed with ice and hydrochloric acid and again extracted with ether. The combined ethereal extracts were thoroughly washed with water, acid and alkali. After drying over calcium chloride, the solvent was removed and the residue distilled at 122-27°/7 mm. and contained much dissolved sulphur which was removed by boiling in dry benzene solution with precipitated copper for a few hours. From the benzene filtrate the nitrile was obtained as a clear colourless oil, b.p. 118-20°/5 mm., yield 7·5 g. from two similar experiments. The dehydration takes place better when small quantities were employed. (Found : N, 7·6. $C_{12}H_{19}ON$ requires N, 7·25 per cent).

Ethyl (1-Methyl-1-β-ethoxyethyl-2-cyano-Δ²-cyclohexenoyl)-formate (V).—Potassium (13·8 g.), placed under ether, was treated with absolute alcohol (70 c.c. freshly distilled over calcium) and heated under reflux until complete solution. A portion of the ether was evaporated off through the condenser avoiding formation of solid crusts. After cooling in a freezing mixture, ice-cold pure ethyl oxalate (25 c.c.) was added and the mixture allowed to stand for 10 minutes. To the mixture a cooled solution of the nitrile (31 g.) in freshly distilled pyridine (60 c.c.) was added slowly with shaking. The solution became at first deep violet and then blood-red. After standing in ice-chest for 36 hours the solution was decomposed with ice when the potassium salt separated, which dissolved on further dilution. The reddish alkaline solution was extracted with ether whence the unsaturated nitrile (8 g.) was recovered. The alkaline solution furnished a heavy oil on acidification with dilute sulphuric acid which was extracted with ether and the ethereal extract was washed with water and dried. The residue from ether distilled at 168-70°/2 mm. as a viscous gum having a light yellow colour. It gave a deep violet ferric reaction in alcoholic solution, yield 24 g (Found : C, 65·2; H, 7·5. $C_{16}H_{23}O_4N$ requires C, 65·46; H, 7·8 per cent).

Methyl 1-Methyl-1-β-ethoxyethyl-2-cyanocyclohexane-4-carboxylate (VI).—To the cyanoketo-ester (V, 16 g.), dissolved in methyl alcohol (50 c.c.), was

added with shaking a solution of sodium hydroxide (9.5 g.) in water (75 c.c.), the mixture became hot and was allowed to stand at room temperature for 2 days and then refluxed for 1 hour on the steam-bath. After acidification with ice-cold sulphuric acid, the precipitated oil was extracted with ether, the extract dried in vacuum for a day and the resulting reddish mass dissolved in pyridine (100 c.c.). Hydrogen peroxide (5 c.c. of 0.012 g. of oxygen per c.c.) was added and the temperature was gradually raised to 60° and a further quantity (4 c.c.) of hydrogen peroxide added. After keeping the mixture at 60° for 1 hour, it was poured into ice-cold sulphuric acid and extracted twice with ether. The residue from ether was reduced with sodium amalgam (3%, 700 g.), the mixture being kept nearly neutral with sulphuric acid. The acidic solution was extracted with ether, dried over sodium sulphate, and the gummy residue (11.5 g.) from ether dried in vacuum. It was dissolved in methyl alcohol (100 c.c.) and esterified with hydrogen chloride and the product isolated in the usual way, b.p. 145-48°/2 mm., yield 8 g. (Found: C, 66.7; H, 8.6. $C_{14}H_{22}O_3N$ requires C, 66.4; H, 9.01 per cent).

Ethyl 2-Methyl-1-(β-bromoethyl)-hexahydroisophthalate (VI, R=Br).—The cyano-ester (VI, 15 g.) was heated with hydrobromic acid (48%, 53 c.c.) in a sealed tube for 6 hours at 140-50° and after dilution with water the heavy oily layer was extracted with ether and washed with sodium bisulphite solution. The dark oil (6.5 g.) from ether, after drying in *vacuo*, was treated with phosphorus pentabromide (20 g.) and left overnight, when a nearly complete solution resulted. After addition of absolute alcohol (50 c.c.) the mixture was allowed to stand for some time and finally heated on the steam-bath for 3 hours. On working up in the usual way, two fractions were collected. The first fraction (2 g.) had b.p. 133-38°/3.5 mm. and the second at 156-60°/3.5 mm. (2.5 g.)

The lower boiling fraction gave a very weak test for halogens and the nature of the product is still under investigation. The second fraction was the required bromo-ester (VII, R=Br). (Found: Br, 23.5. $C_{15}H_{22}O_4Br$ requires Br, 22.8 per cent).

Ethyl (1-Methyl-2:4-dicarbethoxy-cyclohexan)-1-propionate.—The bromo-ester (VII, R=Br; 2.5 g.) was treated with an aqueous alcoholic solution of potassium cyanide (1.5 g.) in presence of a little sodium iodide. The product after refluxing for 15 hours, was isolated in the usual way. Its ethereal solution was dried and directly esterified with alcohol (40 c.c.) and sulphuric acid (d 1.84, 8 c.c.) and two fractions isolated. The fraction (1 g.)

(b.p. 165-78°/1 mm.) was redistilled at 170-75°/1 mm. (lit. 170°/2 mm.). The quantity (0.5 g.) was, however, too small to permit further purification. (Found : C, 62.3 ; H, 8.2. $C_{18}H_{30}O_6$ requires C, 63.1 ; H, 8.7 per cent).

Further work is in progress.

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